

DIGITAL SOFTWARE AS A MEANS OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF PHYSICS EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article, Digital Educational Technologies are understood as technologies for managing the design, organization, monitoring, evaluation and individualization of educational processes based on modern digital tools such as computers, the Internet, mobile devices, artificial intelligence, multimedia, cloud platforms, AR/VR (augmented and virtual reality). These tools redefine the traditional roles between the teacher and the student, forming the student not as a consumer of knowledge, but as a creator of knowledge. The role of digital technologies in the modern education system is increasingly increasing. Digital educational technologies are an important tool in making the learning process more interactive, effective and individually focused. It is argued that they provide an opportunity not only to understand knowledge, but also to consolidate it through experience, simulation and visual materials.*

Keywords: *digital, technology, computer, internet, mobile, devices, artificial intelligence, multimedia, cloud platforms, interactive, individual.*

INTRODUCTION. In the global education system, the integration of science and production, the improvement of the educational process through digital software tools, the expansion of students’ opportunities for independent learning, and the acceleration of the learning process through the introduction of distance education technologies have been identified as priority tasks. In particular, within the framework of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030, ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education has been defined as a major objective. The document emphasizes the development of education based on modern technologies and the expansion of learning opportunities for all ages: “Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.”

Worldwide, there is an increasing implementation of independent learning models (Simulations), distance learning systems such as Moodle, Ilias, Dokeos, and others. In the context of the information-educational environment (e-learning), the continuity and practical orientation of education, the development of learners’ creative abilities, and the enhancement of their readiness for innovative professional activity are gaining importance. Consequently, the improvement of methods for using educational software tools has become a key factor, as digital software serves as an essential means of improving the quality of physics education.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY. In recent years, priority tasks have been set in Uzbekistan to “create new textbooks and alternative materials for academic lyceums specializing in advanced physics education based on improved curricula, and to renew material, technical, laboratory, and instructional resources.” The implementation of educational software tools and problem-based teaching technologies in teaching the section “Quantum Physics” plays a significant role in developing students’ critical thinking skills.

M. Dzhurayev's textbook "Methods of Teaching Physics (General Issues)" aims to improve the quality of training physics teachers within the continuous education system and is regarded as one of the modern works in this field. The manual, based on the state educational standards for the "Quantum Physics" program, provides valuable methodological insights. In his research, D. M. Ismoilov conducts a methodological analysis of quantum physics as a fundamental physical theory. A. Kholmatov and G. Karimova propose innovative methods for teaching physics, while D. S. Sharipova focuses on methodological analysis in this area, enriching the theoretical foundation of the present study. Moreover, M. Kh. Islomova and A. Karimov have suggested new approaches to teaching physics using mobile applications, simulations, and animations.

RESULTS. The reviewed dissertations reveal the pedagogical conditions and didactic possibilities for enhancing professional-pedagogical creativity. They also identify the nature and indicators of students' competencies in physics, and propose an innovative methodology for teaching topics related to natural and alternative energy sources within an integrated media-education system. Furthermore, the studies describe how the stages of professional preparation in physics lessons are summarized and expanded, with empirical concepts and systematic approaches to directing practical and theoretical knowledge supported by well-developed information-methodological resources. At the same time, modern pedagogical approaches—such as problem-based learning, interactive methods, and project-based instruction—are increasingly being applied in teaching physics. These approaches contribute to developing students' critical thinking, research, collaboration, communication, and problem-solving skills, thereby strengthening their overall learning experience.

However, an analysis of the educational process shows that not all lyceums are equally equipped with modern learning technologies, virtual laboratories, and interactive platforms. This situation creates certain difficulties, especially in explaining topics such as quantum physics through visualization, modeling, and experimentation. The introduction of modern learning platforms, simulation tools, and electronic textbooks and applications based on the STEAM approach can help address these needs and serve as a solution to pressing educational challenges.

DISCUSSION. In the modern education system, the role of digital technologies is steadily increasing. Digital learning technologies are essential tools for making the educational process more interactive, efficient, and individually oriented. They provide opportunities not only to understand knowledge but also to reinforce it through experiments, simulations, and visual materials.

Classification of digital technologies:

1. Platform-based systems:

Distance learning platforms (Moodle, Google Classroom, Coursera)
Virtual laboratories (PhET Interactive Simulations, Labster)

2. Interactive tools:

Visual presentation tools (Prezi, Canva)
Simulations and animations (PhET, Algodoo)

3. Assessment systems:

Online tests and quizzes (Kahoot, Quizizz, Mentimeter)

4. AI-based teaching tools: Systems offering individualized learning algorithms (Socratic, Khanmigo)

5. AR/VR technologies: Virtual reality lessons (Google Expeditions, ClassVR)

Table 1. Advantages of Digital Learning Technologies

Type of technology	Advantages
Virtual laboratories	Opportunity to conduct practical experiments
Online assessment tools	Instant and automated control and analysis
Artificial intelligence	Individual approach and adaptive learning
Mobile applications	Convenience, accessibility anytime and anywhere
AR/VR technologies	Deep understanding of the topic through the effect of realism

When we hear the term *software*, we usually imagine processes carried out with the help of a computer. It is difficult to imagine any activity in today's world without the Internet. Computer and Internet — one cannot exist without the other. Before accessing the Internet, a computer must have the necessary software installed. The main program for working on the global network is called a “browser,” and nowadays, many such browsers have been developed by specialists. For example:

- In the Windows operating system, this function is performed by the “Internet Explorer” (IE) program;
- The “Opera” browser, which is known for loading web pages faster and having a more user-friendly interface than Internet Explorer;
- The “FireFox” browser, which also has many advantages over IE;
- Various download manager programs (ReGet, FlashGet, GetRight);
- Microsoft Office programs (Word, Excel, PowerPoint);
- The Acrobat Reader program (for viewing “PDF” files);
- The WinDjView program (for viewing “djvu” files);
- Archiver programs such as WinZip and WinRar;
- Translation programs such as Prompt, Socrat, Stylus, and Spells.

There are many more similar computer programs that could be listed. Moreover, each computer program has a specific purpose and meaning according to its function. Software is being developed for all sectors of the national economy, and it is now impossible to imagine the operation of any field without them. Activities organized on the basis of computer programs are referred to as *software-based activities*.

The general tasks and directions of software tools include:

- Creating a unified electronic database of software developers in our country and supporting talented young programmers who are engaged in developing promising projects and innovative computer technologies;
- Forming a database of national software products and providing information about the state and potential of the software production market in our country.

Software tools are a logically organized set of operations, commands, and data presented in an algorithmic language, intended to be executed on a computer to achieve a specific result.

Software is a tool designed to perform a certain type of task on a computer. It is software that transformed the computer from “bare metal” into an “intelligent device.” Software includes

all the programs used by a computer. In English, the term *software* is derived from “soft” (meaning flexible) and “ware” (meaning product). Software is divided into three main groups:

1. **System software** – includes programs that perform various auxiliary functions, such as Task Manager (available in Windows OS);
2. **Application software** – includes programs designed to process and handle data in a specific field of use, for example: Microsoft Office, Adobe CC;
3. **Programming software** – includes programs used for developing and writing other software.

Technology now assists with computing, reasoning, and working with all kinds of data sets. Below are the main types of system software for computers, along with their brief descriptions. Any modern computer—whether a desktop, laptop, or server—operates on the same fundamental principle. If unnecessary elements are removed, every program, even the simplest one, is built according to a similar algorithm. Actions must be performed step by step, where each next stage begins only after the previous one is completed. Characters entered from the keyboard appear on the screen; after the user issues a print command, the printer starts printing them on paper; and after a formula is entered, calculations are automatically executed.

Every step is pre-programmed and represents a *command* for the computer, while the collection of these steps is represented by code, which forms a program. Specialists who develop and customize software are known as *programmers*. They can control a personal computer with a single line of code that contains encoded data segments. A specific sequence of characters can start music playback, send a document to print, or open a particular webpage on the Internet. The peculiarity of modern software lies in the fact that a wide variety of programs with different functions constantly operate and interact within a computer system. There are programs that perform arithmetic calculations, create charts, draw diagrams, or help users stay connected via email or messaging. However, nothing operates independently — everything functions under the control of the *operating system*.

Large automatic production machines, computers, and other complex mechanisms typically work in a mode that repeats the same algorithm continuously. However, for a personal computer, repeating the same command endlessly is impractical. Software types are defined by their functional significance. Without an operating system, all functions and algorithms would have to be combined into a single massive code, requiring enormous time and effort. The operating system takes on most routine tasks and allows users to work in a *multitasking mode*. As a result, from two to an unlimited number of editors or visualizers can run simultaneously.

CONCLUSION. Digital software has become a powerful transformational tool in enhancing the quality of physics education. It not only makes the learning process more interactive, visual, and participatory but also significantly improves students’ comprehension, independent thinking, and analytical skills. With the help of modern AR/VR technologies, AI-based systems, virtual laboratories, and interactive simulations, it is now possible to teach complex topics such as quantum physics in an engaging and comprehensible way. Global experience and scientific-theoretical research confirm the effectiveness of these tools. Therefore, integrating digital software into physics education is not merely a trend of the times—it has become a necessary stage that ensures depth, continuity, and effectiveness in the learning process.

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